

Rahn (Pawn) on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the map of research developments regarding Rahn Agreements in Islamic Financial Inclusion. The research was conducted from 2003 to 2022 by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Akad Rahn". Based on the search results, there were 268 research articles, which were then input into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a Library Research study. The research results show that the number of publications has increased significantly every year. And based on the mapping results using the VOSviewer application, research around Akad Rahn is divided into 5 clusters and 155 topic items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a Library Research study, there are 10 main themes surrounding Rahn Agreements in Islamic Financial Inclusion.

Keywords: Rahn (Pawn); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Inclusion

Introduction

In this modern era, people need financing that is easy to obtain, fast processing, and in accordance with sharia principles. Internal challenges consist of employees' lack of understanding of sharia principles, a lack of trained professionals, poor institutional vision and mission, and limited storage space for collateral. Apart from that, the rahn contract also faces external challenges, such as not being widely known by the public, threats from conventional bank products, threats to the security of collateral, and the view that the rahn contract is always related to religion.

Institution finance sharia own task main in financing And distribution of funds. As Wrong One type financing, contract rahn (pawn sharia) is part from the various models and types of financing available. The rahn contract cannot be separated from the ijarah (rental) contract in its application. Apart from that, in practice, rahn contracts are often used in financial transactions at sharia banks, where customers can provide valuables as collateral to obtain a loan. If the customer doesn't capable pay loan, bank sharia can sell goods guarantee the to cover unpaid loans. However, in a rahn contract, the terms and conditions must comply with Islamic law.

Scientific publications related to the Rahn contract have increased over the years to year. If explored through website Garuda (Garba Reference Digital) on year in 2020, there were 48 studies related to the rahn contract. This figure is the highest number over the last 19 years. This indicates that this rahn contract will continue to be used as an object of research and will continue to be refined along with the development of information and the need for answers to problems in modern society.

This research aims to map the development of research and publication of scientific articles related to the Rahn di contract Islamic Financial Inclusion during over the last 19 years, namely from 2003 to 2022 using research methods in the form of VOSviewer bibliometrics and Library Research studies.

Literature Review

Rahn contract is a contract where a recipient of goods (murtahin) has the right to retain goods (maroon) as guarantee on debt or can interpreted as

replacement payment if the party who has the debt (rahn) fails to pay off the debt. In a rahn contract, the pawnbroker hands over the goods used as collateral to the pawnee, while the pawnee gives a loan of money or something else to the pledgor. This Rahn contract is additional in nature where this contract is usually applied side by side with other contracts such as sale and purchase contracts (bai'), rental contracts (ijarah) and qardh contracts.

Bibliometric studies are an analytical method used to measure and evaluate the performance and impact of scientific publications. This method involves the use of statistics to calculate and analyze the characteristics of scientific publications, including the number of publications, number of citations, and frequency of citations. The main aim of bibliometric studies is to identify trends in scientific publications and to evaluate the performance of researchers, journals, or institution based on criteria bibliometrics certain. Studies bibliometrics Also used to gain insight into the influence of scientific publications on the development of knowledge in a particular field. This method has been used widely in various scientific disciplines, including social sciences, natural sciences, computer science, and humanities. VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities-viewer) is one of the open-source software used in bibliometric studies. This software can be used to analyze the relationship between keywords, authors and scientific publications based on bibliometric data.

Study Library Research is process systematic Which done For identify, evaluate, and synthesize literature or references related to a specific research topic or problem. In a Library Research, a researcher will search and analyze various sources of information such as scientific journals, books, reports, and others. Literature studies can be used as a theoretical basis that will help researchers in designing And formulate question study Which relevant, as well as in planning the design study Which appropriate And methodology study appropriate with objective study.

Methodology

This research uses research method with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is the Rahn Agreement at Islamic Financial Inclusion. Type of data used is data secondary. Room scope data Which used is article Scientific publications about Akad Rahn originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then searching for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " Akad Rahn " and "Gadai" throughout the year (2003-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) downloading files format RIS (Research Information Systems) And PDF (Portable Document Format) from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Technique analysis data includes: (1) map files data RIS on Mendeley Desktop based on order year, writer, And publisher; (2) map results visualization network bibliometrics and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on Library Research studies.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Spread Publication Scientific About Contract Rahn/Pawn on Institution Sharia Finance

Search results for scientific articles discussing Rahn/Pawn contracts in

Islamic Financial Inclusion during the period 2003 to November 2022 have increased every year, especially in the last 5 years. 2021 was recorded as the year with the highest number of scientific article publications, namely 50 articles in one year. This figure is also the highest number of publications over the last 5 years. So, on average, the number of scientific publications regarding the Rahn/Gadai contract is 17 articles per year.

Table 1. Data publication scientific around contract Rahn/Pawn based on year

Year of Publication	Amount Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Amount Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Amount Publication Articles
2003	1	2013	15	2018	30
2007	1	2014	11	2019	33
2008	1	2015	12	2020	47
2009	2	2016	24	2021	50
2010	1	2017	21	2022	16
2012	3				
Amount 268					

Source: Data processed, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, is data affiliation/institution with amount publication article The most scientific research is related to research on Rahn/Pawn contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion. The Faculty of Law Student Journal Collection is a journal publishing institution with the highest number of publications, reaching 6 articles about Rahn/Gadai contracts.

Table 2. Affiliate/institution publisher journal around contract Rahn/Pawn

Name Affiliates/Institutions	Number of Publications
Gathering Journal Student Faculty Law	6
Journal Economy Sharia Theory And Applied, Journal Justisia Ekonomika: Master of Sharia Economic Law	5
Journal Scientific Al- Shir'ah	4
Al-Iqtishad: Journal of Sharia Economics, Journal of Buana Accounting, Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics, FEB Student Scientific Journal, Journal of Science Accountancy And Business Sharia (AKSY), Journal On line Student (JOM) Field Knowledge Law, PREMISES LAW JOURNAL	3
Al-Amwal : Journal Economy And Banking Sharia, AL-INFAQ, An-Nisbah: Journal of Sharia Economics, An-Nisbah: Journal of Sharia Banking, Ar-Ribh : Journal Economy Islam, Ash-Shari'ah, Eco- Iqtishodi : Scientific Journal of Sharia Economics and Finance, EKSISBANK (Sharia Economics and Banking Business), El-Mal: Journal of Economic Studies & Business Islam, Law Islam, IQTISHADIA: Journal Sharia Economics & Banking, ISLAMINOMICS: JOURNAL OF ISLAMIC ECONOMICS, BUSINESS AND FINANCE, JIAGABI (Journal Knowledge Commerce/Business Administration), Journal of Sharia Banking, Accounting Journal AKUNESA, Journal Law Economy Sharia, Journal	2

Based on results analysis, so obtained 5 cluster And 155 topic, that is:

- Cluster 1. Red, consists of 54 topics, namely: amount, application, ar rahn, business, community, condition, customer, customer interest, customer satisfaction, data, data collection technique, development, distribution, effect, financial institution, financing, fund, gold price, income, increase, Indonesia, inflation, inflation rate, influence, interest, Islamic pawnshop, member, murabahah, pawnshop, pawnshop, sharia pawnshop, sharia pawnshop, person, price, primary data, profit, promotion, provision, PT pawn shop, quality, rahn, rahn financing, rahn products, research, research methods, researchers, respondent, secondary data, service, service quality, sharia pawn, sharia pawnshop, significant effect, value.
- Cluster 2. Color green consists from 35 topic, that is: agreement, auctions, benefits, collateral, concept, cost, debt, difference, DSN MUI IV, executed, guarantee, guarantee Islam, guarantee, law, maintenance, marhun, money, mortgage, murtahin, object, obligation, paddy field, pawn, perspective, practice, property, rahin, rahn tasjily, repayment, sale, rice fields, sharia economic law, society, terms, transactions.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 34 topics, namely: agree, addition, contract, determination, documentation, DSN, DSN MUI, DSN MUI III, fatwa, fields, fields research, form, gold pawning, ijarah contract, implementation, institution, interview, Islamic bank, Islamic law, loan, mechanism, need, observation, pawning, principle, problem, quality approach, rahn contract, requirement, rice field, sharia principle, thing, ujarah way.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 30 topics, namely: accounting treatment, banks, Bank Indonesia, sharia banks, gold, pawning, gold pawn, gold, gold pawn, hadith, ijara, ijarah, Islamic bank, Islamic banking, orders, financing, pledge, procedure, product, product, psak, qardh, qualitative method, regulation, rule, sfas, sharia, bank sharia, sharia, system.
- Cluster 5. Color purple consists from 2 topic, that is: pawn sharia, Marhun eh.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Application Contract Rahn/Pawn

A rahn contract or pawn contract is a form of contract or agreement in sharia finance which is generally used as collateral or collateral in providing loans. or financing. In contract rahn, party giver loan give loans or financing to the borrower by requesting collateral in the form of certain goods or property (Budianto, 2023).

The application of the rahn contract in Islamic Financial Inclusion, such as sharia banks or sharia microfinance institutions, is usually carried out with the following process: (1) Identification of collateral, namely the lender must determine the type of goods or property that can be used as collateral, as well as determine the value of the collateral or the market price of the goods; (2) Collateral appraisal, namely the lender must assess the value of the collateral in a way objective And ensure that mark collateral equivalent with mark loan or financing provided; (3) Making an agreement, namely after the collateral has been determined and assessed, party giver loan And borrower must make agreement pawn or rahn agreement Which load information related goods Which made collateral, mark collateral, payment terms loan or financing, as well as terms auction or sale collateral if the borrower No can pay return loan or financing; (4) Submission collateral, namely after the pawn agreement is made, the collateral must be handed over to the lender and stored safely until the loan or financing is paid off and the collateral is returned to the borrower; and (5) Sale of collateral, namely if the borrower cannot pay return loan or financing, party giver loan entitled For sell collateral to compensate for losses suffered. However, the sale of collateral must be carried out in a legal and fair

manner, and the remaining sales proceeds after deducting costs must be returned to the borrower (Dewi et al., 2023).

Application contract rahn on institution finance sharia must notice sharia principles and Islamic law, so it must be carried out in a transparent, honest, And fair. In sub-chapter This, there is 8 topic study around application contract Rahn/Pawn on Inclusion Finance Sharia, that is: (1) Implementation in Pawnshop Sharia; (2) Application in Sharia Banks; (3) Implementation in Baitul Maal wa Tamwiil; (4) Implementation in Sharia People's Financing Banks; (5) Application in Malaysia; (6) Application to gold pawn products; (7) Application to agricultural land; and (8) Application to business capital for Medium, Small and Micro Enterprises.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Influence Contract Rahn/Pawn

Rahn contract or pawn guarantee is a type of contract or agreement in the sharia financial system that allows someone to borrow money by providing guarantee on asset Which he has. Influence contract rahn on institution finances can be shared into several aspects (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023), between other:

- Reduce credit risk. By providing collateral for assets owned by borrowers, Islamic financial institutions can reduce credit risks that may arise consequence inability borrower For pay return loan. Pawn guarantee This can become guarantee For protect interest institution finance and prevent losses.
- Increase borrower confidence. The existence of this rahn agreement can provide a sense of security and trust to borrowers because the assets they pledge can be taken back after loan paid off, so give certainty that the assets will return to their possession.
- Add source income institution finance. Institution finance sharia can also benefit from this rahn contract. In the event of default or inability of the borrower to repay the loan, the financial institution can sell asset Which guaranteed with price Which more tall from loan given, so that you can make a profit.
- Encourage business development. With the existence of a rahn agreement, Islamic Financial Inclusion can increase financial access for the public to obtain business capital. This can encourage business and broader economic development.
- Strengthening the sharia financial system. Rahn contracts can also strengthen the financial system sharia in a way whole with give alternative for society in obtaining fairer and more sustainable access to finance.

Overall, the influence of rahn contracts on financial institutions is positive and provides many benefits for society and the economy at large.

In this sub-chapter, there are 10 research topics regarding the influence of the Rahn/Gadai contract on Inclusion Finance Sharia, that is: (1) The influence to profitability company; (2) Its influence on economic empowerment; (3) The effect on increasing customer income; (4) The effect on financing distribution; (5) The influence on people's interest in making transactions at sharia banks; (6) The effect on company income; (7) Its influence on the progress of sharia banking; (8) The effect on company profits; (9) Its effect on profit levels; and (10) Its influence on community productivity.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around View Law Islam, Law Positive and Legislation regarding Rahn/Pawn Agreements

According to the view of Islamic law, a rahn or pawn contract is a contract made with collateral, where the party giving the guarantee (rahn) hands over something of value to the party receiving the guarantee (murtahin), as collateral for debt payment or fulfillment of other obligations. In a rahn or pawn contract, the party providing collateral still has the rights to the goods pledged as collateral and

can take them return goods the after debt or obligation Which guaranteed has fulfilled (Budianto & Dewi, 2023).

According to positive law in Indonesia, rahn or pawn contracts are regulated in Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees and Minister of Finance Regulation Number 168/PMK.06/2012 about Pawn on Object Move Which Mastered by Party Other. According to Constitution the, contract rahn or pawn is something agreement between the guarantor with the collateral recipient, where the guarantor hands over the movable objects he owns to the collateral recipient as collateral for debts or obligations that must be fulfilled. The amount of debt or obligation guaranteed must be clear and stated in contract. Recipient guarantee No can deliver object move that to the other party during the debt or guaranteed obligations Not yet fulfilled. After If the debt or obligation is fulfilled, the collateral recipient must immediately return the movable object to the collateral provider (Rohimah et al., 2023).

In this sub-chapter, there are 15 research topics regarding views of Islamic law, positive law and Rahn/Pawn contract legislation on Sharia Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Application according to the DSN-MUI fatwa; (2) Application of Rahn accounting according to PSAK No. 107 and 102; (3) Determination of *ujrah*/wages in Rahn financing according to the DSN-MUI fatwa; (4) Rahn Agreement in the compilation of Sharia Economic Law; (5) Implementation according to sharia principles; (6) Implementation of the *ijarah* contract in Rahn's practice from a Sharia Economic Law perspective; (7) The concept of interpreting Rahn's verses using a scholarly approach; (8) Rahn contract clauses from the perspective of Islamic law; (9) Trademark rights as the object of the Rahn agreement according to Islamic law; (10) Expenses for storage and maintenance of Rahn objects according to Civil law; (11) Utilization of pawned goods according to ulama; (12) Rahn *Tasjily* agreement according to fatwa DSN-MUI; (13) Factors shaper fees *ijarah* (PSAK 107) to portfolio Rahn gold; (14) *Al-Tamwil Al-Mautsuq bil-Rahn* according to the DSN-MUI Fatwa; and (15) Legal protection for Rahn contract customers.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Effort Development Contract Rahn/Pawn

Effort development contract rahn/pawn on sector finance can done through several methods (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023), including:

- Increase awareness public will benefit contract rahn/pawn as sharia and halal alternative financing. One way to increase public awareness is to provide education and outreach regarding the principles and benefits of rahn/gadai contracts through various media.
- Expanding the reach and improving the quality of rahn/pawn contract services by utilizing technology. Technology can be used to facilitate the transaction process and speed up the disbursement of funds, so that customers feel it is easier and more comfortable to use rahn/pawn contract services.
- Increase quality product contract rahn/pawn with offer ethnic group flower more competitive and faster service. This can be done by streamlining administration and risk management processes, thereby reducing operational costs and offering more competitive interest rates.
- Building collaborations with other financial institutions. Financial institutions can collaborate with sharia banks or other sharia financing institutions to increase accessibility and expand the reach of rahn/pawn contract services.
- Expanding the types of goods that can be pawned by following developments in market trends and needs. In developing rahn/pawn contract products, institution finance can offer type goods Which can more diverse things are pawned, such as jewelry, gadgets, vehicles, etc.

Through these efforts, it is hoped that the rahn/pawn contract will be

developed in the sector finance can the more develop And give benefit Which more big for people who need financing.

In this sub-chapter, there are 10 research topics regarding efforts to develop Rahn/Pawn contracts for Sharia Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Marketing strategies for sharia pawn products; (2) Development of the Rahn concept in Sharia Pawnshops; (3) Application of the Sugeno fuzzy method in determining the amount of Rahn financing; (4) Application of Rahn Tasjily in Institutions Finance Sharia; (5) Integration contract financing And Rahn; (6) Application SWOT in Rahn's contract; (7) Strategy in dealing with pawn product development; (8) Application of pawn application data; (9) Pawning of gold as a sharia investment instrument; and (10) Financial Technology in the Rahn agreement.

Mapping Library Research Studies around Factors that Influence People's Interest in Using Rahn Products

Several factors that can influence people's interest in using Rahn products at financial institutions are:

- Trust in financial institutions: People will be more interested in using them Rahn products from institution finance Which own reputation who is good and trustworthy in handling financial transactions.
- Convenience access: Convenience in access product Rahn, like location offices that are easy to reach and the existence of digital services can increase people's interest in using Rahn products.
- Interest rates: The interest rates offered by financial institutions on Rahn products can be one of the factors that influence people's interest in using these products.
- Product flexibility: Rahn products that are flexible and can be adapted to people's needs can increase people's interest in using these products.
- Security: People will be more interested in using Rahn products from financial institutions that guarantee the security of Rahn products and follow applicable sharia rules.
- Service Which Good: Service Which Good from institution finance, like Fast and responsive service to complaints can increase people's interest in using Rahn products.

In this sub-chapter, there are 30 research topics regarding factors that influence people's interest in using Rahn/Gadai products in Sharia Financial Inclusion, that is: (1) Convenience; (2) Profit; (3) Security; (4) Trust; (5) Service; (6) Service fees/ujrah; (7) Promotion; (8) Age; (9) Education; (10) Employment; (11) Income; (12) Household expenses; (13) Number of family dependents; (14) Knowledge; (15) Image institution; (16) Accessibility; (17) Religiosity; (18) Application principle sharia; (19) Condition (Covid-19); (20) Location; (21) Mark estimate; (22) Liquidity gold; (23) Condition; (24) Price; (25) Guarantee; (26) Information; (27) Proof physique; (28) Reliability; (29) Responsiveness; and (30) Empathy.

Mapping Library Research Studies regarding Factors that Influence Rahn/Pawn Distribution

Rahn or Pawn Distribution is a financial service that can help people obtain cash by providing collateral for valuables such as gold, jewelry or motor vehicles. However, there are several factors that influence the distribution of mortgages or pawns to financial institutions (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023), including:

- Need market. Institution finance will channel Rahn/Pawn in accordance with market needs. If demand for Rahn/Pawn is high, then financial institutions will offer these products more aggressively. On the other hand, if demand is low, then the supply of Rahn/Gadai products will be less.
- Interest rate. The interest rate offered by financial institutions can also

influence people's interest in using Rahn/Gadai services. If the interest rate is high, then people will think twice before using this service, because they will be burdened with high interest costs. On the other hand, if the interest rate is low, people will be more interested in using this service.

- The value of collateral. The value of the guarantee provided by the customer also influences the distribution of Rahn/Pawn at the institution finance. The more tall collateral value, the easier it is for customers to obtain funds from financial institutions. However, financial institutions will also consider the risks of the collateral.
- Ability to repay. Financial institutions will consider the customer's ability to repay the loaned funds. Therefore That, customers Which own history credit Which Good And own ability Having sufficient finances will make it easier to obtain funds from financial institutions.
- Internal policies of financial institutions. Internal policies of financial institutions such as administrative requirements, procedures and risk policies can also influence the distribution of Rahn/Gadai. Financial institutions will determine terms and conditions that must be fulfilled by customers in order to obtain funds from the Rahn/Gadai service.
- Competition between financial institutions. Competition between financial institutions also influences Rahn/Gadai distribution. Financial institutions will compete to offer lower interest rates or terms and conditions that are easier to fulfill in order to attract more customers. This will affect market competition and the number of customers who use Rahn/Pawn services at financial institutions.

In this sub-chapter, there are 9 research topics surrounding the factors that influence the distribution of Rahn/Pawn on Sharia Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Inflation; (2) Business Income; (3) Exchange rate; (4) Gold price; (5) Number of customers; (6) Poor population; (7) Profit margin; (8) BI Rate; and (9) Company size.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors Which Influence Earning Rahn/Pawn Profits

Acquisition profit rahn or pawn on institution finance sharia like bank Sharia, takaful companies and sharia cooperative loan companies are influenced by various factors. Several factors that influence the acquisition of rahn/pawn profits at Islamic Financial Inclusion include:

- Interest Rate: The interest rate is the main factor that influences profit generation rahn/pawn at the institution finance sharia. The higher the interest rate, the higher the profit generated.
- Asset Quality: The quality of assets or the suitability of the collateral used in pawning transactions also influences the acquisition of rahn/pawn profits. The higher the quality of the assets, the greater the likelihood that the collateral will not lose value, thereby minimizing the risk of loss for Islamic financial institutions.
- Market Competition: The level of market competition also influences the acquisition of rahn/pawn profits at Islamic financial institutions. The more financial institutions that offer mortgage/pawn products, the more difficult it is for financial institutions to maintain their market share and maximize profits.
- Condition Economy: Condition economy Which stable can give impact positive in obtaining rahn/pawn profits at Islamic Financial Inclusion. On the other hand, economic conditions Which No stable can cause risk fail pay Which more tall and has an impact on reducing profits.
- Government Policy: Government policy regarding regulation and supervision of Islamic financial institutions can also influence the acquisition of rahn/pawn profits. Policy Which support growth industry finance sharia can have a positive impact on the acquisition of rahn/pawn profits. However, the

policies are restrictive operation institution finance sharia or enforce burden tax high levels can affect profit generation.

In this sub-chapter, there are 2 research topics regarding the factors that influence the acquisition of Rahn/Pawn profits in Sukuk on Sharia Financial Inclusion, namely: Estimated amount and loan money.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Guarantee/Collateral on Contract Rahn/Pawn

A rahn or pawn contract is a type of contract used by financial institutions to provide financing to their customers with certain guarantees/collateral. The following are several things you need to pay attention to regarding guarantees/collateral in rahn/pawn contracts:

- Collateral/collateral in a rahn/pawn contract is generally in the form of movable goods such as gold, jewelry, vehicles or electronic goods. The amount of financing provided is usually a portion of the value of the guarantee/collateral.
- Customer must deliver guarantee/collateral to the institution finance as a requirement for getting financing. If customers cannot pay off payment obligations, the financial institution has the right to sell the guarantee/collateral to get back the funds that have been provided.
- The process of selling guarantees/collateral must be carried out in a transparent and fair manner. If results of the sale of guarantee/collateral exceed the amount of financing provided, then the remaining funds must be returned to the customer. However, if the proceeds from the sale of collateral/collateral are insufficient to pay off the customer's payment obligations, the customer is still responsible for paying the remaining debt.
- Financial institutions will usually evaluate the quality of the guarantee/collateral before providing financing. This is done to ensure that the value of the guarantee/collateral is equal to or higher than the amount of financing provided, so that the financial institution has sufficient collateral to cover the credit risk it takes.
- Guarantees/collateral in rahn/pawn contracts can be provided by individuals or business entities. However, in the case of business entities, financial institutions will usually ask for documents that prove ownership of the collateral, such as land certificates or vehicle documents.

Customers must maintain the guarantee/collateral properly during the financing period. If there is damage or loss to the guarantee/collateral, the customer remains responsible for paying the remaining debt.

In this sub-chapter, there are 10 research topics regarding guarantees/collateral in Rahn/Gadai on Inclusion Finance Sharia, namely: (1) Guarantee in Rahn financing; (2) Implementation of fiduciary guarantees according to the DSN-MUI fatwa; (3) Mechanism for using material collateral in Rahn financing; (4) Comparison of Law no. 42 of 1999 concerning guarantee fiduciary with fatwa DSN-MUI No. 68; (5) Takeover right on collateral execution fiduciary perspective law positive And Islam; (6) Implementation auction/auction Rahn's collateral has problems; (7) Concept of auction price for pawned collateral; (8) Collateral position between debts and Rahn; (9) Obstacles to the debt and receivables agreement guaranteed by Rahn Tasjily; and (10) Guarantee in the form of a PNS Decree according to the DSN-MUI fatwa.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Perception Public to Rahn/Pawn Agreement

Public perception of rahn/pawn contracts at financial institutions can vary, depending on the culture and background of the people in certain areas. However, generally rahn/gadai contracts are considered as a form of financial solution that allows individuals to obtain cash quickly by providing collateral. in form goods

valuable. A number of public Possible feel No comfortable or distrustful of rahn/pawn contracts because they do not want to relinquish ownership of their valuables. However, on the other hand, there are also those who see the rahn/pawn contract as a safer alternative borrow money from other parties or obtaining funds from unofficial sources.

Several Islamic Financial Inclusion, such as sharia banks or sharia cooperatives, offer contract rahn/pawn in form contract murabahah or contract sell buy, Which in accordance with the principles sharia. Perception public to contract rahn/pawn on Islamic Financial Inclusion are generally more positive because the transactions are in accordance with the principles sharia And considered as alternative Which more halal. By whole, Public perception of rahn/pawn contracts at financial institutions tends to be positive because they are considered an easy and fast way to obtain cash funds. However, it is important to remember that the use of rahn/pawn contracts must be done wisely and responsibly so as not to cause financial problems in the future.

In this sub-chapter, there are 6 research topics regarding public perceptions of contracts Rahn/Pawn on Inclusion Finance Sharia, that is: (1) Perception customers to contract Rahn; (2) Perception of clerics and NU figures; (3) Public perception; (4) Customer satisfaction with the superiority of Rahn's financing products; (5) Customer motivation in Rahn transactions; and (6) Customer satisfaction with Sharia Gadai ijarah rates.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Issues Other Which Related with Rahn/Pawn Agreement

In this sub-chapter, there are 25 Research topics revolve around other issues related to Rahn/Pawn contracts in Sharia Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Rahn Products in Islamic Financial Inclusion; (2) Benefits of sharia gold pawn financing; (3) Shariah Compliance with the Rahn contract; (4) Social history of the development of Rahn's law; (5) Problematize implementation financing Rahn; (6) Hybrid contracts in financing Rahn; (7) Implementation of the ijarah agreement on Rahn products; (8) Opportunities, challenges and criticism in the gold pawn contract; (9) The moral value of the Ijarah contract and the wages in the Rahn contract; (10) The urgency of the notary in the Rahn contract; (11) Rahn Agreement Clause; (12) Gala (customary pawn) and Rahn; (13) Internal control over Rahn distribution; (14) Evaluation of the application of Gadai/Rahn accounting; (15) Not quite enough answer murtahin (recipient pawn) in implementation contract Rahn gold; (16) Qardh agreement in Rahn financing; (17) Determining the fairness of prices for financing Rahn; (18) Application multi contract on financing Rahn; (19) Imposition Rahn administrative costs; (20) Settlement of disputes when an error in Rahn's product assessment occurs; (21) Settlement of problematic financing/bad credit in the Rahn agreement; (22) Settlement of defaults in the pawn agreement; (23) Differences in application between conventional mortgages and mortgages sharia; (24) Risk management in the Rahn contract; and (25) Evaluation of Rahn's contract reporting.

Conclusion

Based on results discussion on, can concluded as following:

- Number of research publications regarding Rahn Agreements in Islamic Financial Inclusion during period time year 2003 until year 2022, show enhancement significantly from year to year. Amount total publication is 268 article study, which comes from international journals indexed by Scopus, international journals and national journals indexed by Sinta.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the Faculty of Law Student Journal Collection. The total number of publications is 6 research articles.
- Researcher Which most productive publish results study is Fachrudin Riqri

Affandy from IAIN Fattahul Grandiose Papua Which write article scientific as much 3 article.

- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, the development of research regarding the Rahn Agreement in Islamic Financial Inclusion is divided into 5 clusters and 155 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 54 topics, cluster 2 consists of 35 topics, cluster 3 consists of 34 topics, cluster 4 consists of 30 topics, and cluster 5 consists of 5 topics.
- Based on Library Research review, there are 11 main research theme regarding the Rahn Agreement in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Application of the Rahn/Pawn agreement; (2) Influence contract Rahn/Pawn; (3) View law Islam, law positive and legislation to contract Rahn/Pawn; (4) Development contract Ijarah; (5) Factors that influence the Ijarah contract; (6) Factors that influence public interest in the Ijarah contract; (7) Implementation of the Ijarah contract in Sukuk; (8) Factors Which influence Sukuk Ijarah; (9) Application contract Ijarah Muntahiya Bit Tamlik (IMBT); and (10) Other issues related to the Ijarah contract. Study furthermore recommended use sample data Which more Lots,

so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering sample limitations data in study This And can add range time data study longer so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- Results study Library Research capable explained in a way more complex.

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